

Example Chimpanzee Observations Datasheet

Date:

Focal ID:

Start Time:

End Time:

Focal Behavior

	Scan Time	Focal Behavior	ID 2 (if social)	All IDs near focal	Comments
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					

Grooming

Bout #	Start Time	End Time	Partner ID	Direction	Comments

Aggression

Time	Aggressor ID	Type	Victim ID	Victim Response	Coalition?	Comments

Dominance

Time	Vocalizer ID	Recipient ID	Comments

Tool use

Time	Behavior and Material	Comments